

Simultaneous estimation of aceclofenac and paracetamol in tablets

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Manuscript received 7 March 2005, revised 28 September 2005, accepted 11 November 2005

Abstract : Two simple spectrophotometric methods for the determination of aceclofenac and paracetamol in tablets have been developed. First method is based on the additivity of absorbances. Second method is based on the determination of graphical absorbance ratio at two selected wavelengths; one being the isoabsorptive point for the two drugs (230 nm) and the other being the absorption maximum of paracetamol (256 nm). Beer-Lambert's law is obeyed for both the drugs in the concentration range 1–10 µg/mL. Both the methods were found to be simple, rapid, and accurate and can be adopted in routine analysis of drugs in formulations.

Keywords : Aceclofenac, paracetamol.

Aceclofenac is 2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzoic acid carboxy methyl ester is used as an analgesic and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug. Paracetamol (4-hydroxy acetanilide) is used as an analgesic and anti pyretic drug. Aceclofenac is official in B.P.¹. Paracetamol is official in B.P. and I.P.^{2,3}. A survey of the literature revealed that HPLC⁴, densitometric⁵, spectrofluorimetric⁶ and colorimetric⁷ methods have been reported for the estimation of aceclofenac in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Till now no method has been reported for the simultaneous estimation of the above mentioned drugs in combined dosage forms.

Results and discussion

In the first method, the content of the aceclofenac and paracetamol was directly found from the eqs. (1) and (2). In the second method, the absorbance ratio and the absorptivity coefficients were determined, and the values were substituted in the eq. (4) to give the results. The precision, reproducibility, repeatability and accuracy of these methods were found to be good (Table 1). To test the accuracy and reproducibility of the proposed methods, recovery experiments were performed by adding known amount of the drugs to the preanalyzed formulations and reanalyzing the mixture by proposed methods (Table 2). The percent recovery obtained indicates non-interference from the excipients like starch magnesium stearate etc. if used in the formulations.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

A GBC cintra 10 UV/VIS spectrophotometer with 10

mm matched quartz cells was used for experiments. The chemicals used were of analytical grade. The commercially available tablets of aceclofenac and paracetamol combination Acecloplus (ARISTO) and Fico-p (EMCURE) were procured from local market. Aceclofenac, received as gift sample from Aristo Pharma Ltd. and paracetamol (B.D.H.), were used as such without further purification.

Preparation of standard solutions :

Solutions of aceclofenac and paracetamol were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed 100 mg each of standard aceclofenac and standard paracetamol in 100 mL ethanol. Working standard solutions (A) and (B) were further prepared by taking 1 mL of stock solution of aceclofenac and paracetamol in 10 mL volumetric flasks and making up the volume with ethanol.

Methods of analysis :

Method 1 : (Based on simultaneous equations - Vierodt's method)⁸ :

Overlap spectra of standard solutions of aceclofenac and paracetamol were scanned. Aceclofenac shows absorption maxima at 275 nm and paracetamol shows at 256 nm. The calibration curves for aceclofenac and paracetamol were prepared in the concentration range of 1–10 µg/mL at both the wavelengths i.e. 275 nm and 256 nm. The absorptivity coefficients were determined for both the drugs at both the wavelengths and following equations were made.

$$A_1 = 445.85 C_x + 121.97 C_y \quad (1)$$

$$A_2 = 214.22 C_x + 793.93 C_y \quad (2)$$

Note

A_1 and A_2 are absorbances at 275 and 256 nm respectively and C_x and C_y are concentrations of aceclofenac and paracetamol respectively. The concentrations of both the drugs in the mixture were determined by eqs. (1) and (2).

Method II : Graphical absorbance ratio method :

This method is based on the method used by Ghanem *et al.*⁹ which makes use of the iso-absorptive point of the two drugs i.e. the wavelength of equal absorptivity of the two components of the mixture. The iso-absorptive point was 230 nm (λ_1), in this case. The other wavelength selected is the absorption maximum of one of the components. In this case it was 256 nm, the absorption maximum of paracetamol (λ_2). The concentrations of the two components are related to the ratio of the absorbances at these two wavelengths. The absorbance of the mixture was noted at 256 and 230 nm. Calibration curves of aceclofenac and paracetamol were plotted in the concentration range 1–10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (range for which Beer-Lambert's

law followed). The absorptivity coefficients were determined for both the drugs and the average value was taken. These values and the absorbance ratio were used to develop equations as given below.

$$A_1 = 0.0385 (C_x + C_y) = 0.0385 C_x \left(\frac{-1.5039}{Q_M - 2.0597} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $Q_M = A_2/A_1$ and A_1, A_2 are the absorbances at 230 and 256 nm respectively. C_x and C_y are concentrations of aceclofenac and paracetamol respectively.

Estimation from tablets :

Twenty tablets were weighed and average weight determined. Powder equivalent to 100 mg of paracetamol and 20 mg of aceclofenac was extracted quantitatively with (4 × 20) mL of ethanol. Insoluble excipients were separated by filtration. The supernatant liquid was transferred to 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume made

Table 1. Compilation of results of statistical analysis of commercial formulations

Method	Tablet brand	Tablet composition	Label claim ^a mg/tab	Amount found mg/tab ± S.D.*	S.E. ^a	%R.S.D. ^a	Percentage range of error with in 95% confidence limit ^a
I	Acecloplus	Aceclofenac	100	99.87 ± 0.01	0.0070	0.0100	±0.0149
		Paracetamol	500	500.25 ± 0.01	0.0044	0.0012	±0.0088
	Fico-p	Aceclofenac	100	99.60 ± 0.02	0.0083	0.0117	±0.0163
		Paracetamol	500	499.5 ± 0.01	0.0080	0.0022	±0.0157
II	Acecloplus	Aceclofenac	100	99.60 ± 0.09	0.0510	0.0065	±0.1065
		Paracetamol	500	499.29 ± 0.09	0.0054	0.0071	±0.0156
	Fico-p	Aceclofenac	100	99.12 ± 0.12	0.0126	0.0057	±0.0167
		Paracetamol	500	498.75 ± 0.07	0.0410	0.0059	±0.0915

^aAverage of nine determinations; S.D. = standard deviation; % R.S.D. = relative standard deviation and S.E. = standard error.

Table 2. Compilation of results of drug recovery study

Method	Tablet brand	Aceclofenac		Paracetamol	
		Percent recovery	Standard deviation	Percent recovery	Standard deviation
I	Acecloplus	99.47	0.0234	99.85	0.0150
	Fico-p	99.14	0.0158	99.90	0.0070
II	Acecloplus	98.02	0.0104	98.99	0.0097
	Fico-p	97.91	0.0183	98.90	0.0170

Readings are average of nine determinations.

up with ethanol. The solution so obtained was suitably diluted with ethanol so that the concentration (1–10 µg/mL) can be read directly from the calibration curve, and the absorbances were taken at different wavelengths as stated above. Using the eqs. (1), (2) and (3) the concentrations were determined.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. N. K. Jain, Head of the Department for providing necessary facilities and M/s Aristo Pharma Pvt. Ltd., Mandideep (M.P.) for supplying aceclofenac as a gift sample. The financial assistance received from AICTE in the form of fellowship for post-graduate studies in Engineering and Technology is being gratefully acknowledged by one of the authors (G.G.).

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